

Effects of Methionine Supplementation in Drinking Water of Broiler Chickens at Low and High Environmental Temperatures

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Abstract

One of the main goals of nutritional research is to reduce poultry production costs and increase profits by increasing the utilization of feed and nutrients. An experiment was conducted to investigate the effects of commercially available DL-methionine administered into drinking water at two different temperatures on broiler performance. The effects of methionine added to drinking water at levels of 0.050% and 0.075% were compared with the control diet reported by NRC (National Research Council) for 3-6 weeks. Mortality was not observed by any dietary treatment. Feed intake was not affected adversely by DL-methionine inclusion in drinking water. At two temperatures, birds receiving 0.050% methionine activity in water had lower body weight than those receiving supplemented feed or 0.075% methionine activity in water. These results indicate that, under the study conditions, DL-methionine provided in drinking water can be effectively assimilated by broilers, at least from 21 to 42 days of age.

Keywords: Broilers, drinking water, temperature, DL-methionine

INTRODUCTION

One of the important goals of poultry production is to reduce production costs and maximize profitability by increasing the utilization of feed and nutrients. As a basic physical rule, small particles in a mixture tend to gather at the bottom, while large particles tend to gather at the top (Weast, 1975). The same situation applies to ground feed in poultry farming, where the dry matter constituting the feed separates. In the poultry industry, feeds go through frequent handling, including transportation, before being offered for consumption, and therefore it is difficult to keep the mixture uniform. In addition, studies have shown that chickens prefer particles of 2-3 mm size to smaller ones (Bessei, 1973; Perry et al., 1976). Methionine is an essential amino acid and cannot be synthesized by poultry (Liu et al., 2022). Crystalline DL-methionine particles are very small (300-600 microns) compared to other nutrients in the feed mixture, and the degradation of methionine in commercial feeds is a major problem in this industry. In a study, it was determined that 95% of the crystallized DL-methionine particles were in the bottom 50% of the chicken feeders (Anonymous, 1985), and the ideal mixture is expected to be 50% at the bottom and top. As a result of the segregation, irregularity in the intake of the limiting amino acid will affect protein synthesis in the body (Boorman, 1979), and the decrease in productivity as a result of the chickens not being fed a balanced diet is reflected to the producer as an economic loss. Methionine is necessary for maintenance, egg production, and the formation of body and feather proteins, and is the primary limiting amino acid in commercial chicken diets based on corn-soybean and wheat-soybean (Harms, R. H. et al., 1998). Synthetic methionine has been added to poultry diets since the 1950s (Leong and Mc Ginnis, 1952). Methionine DL form (Damon and Goodson-Williams, 1987) and liquid methionine analog form (Damron and Flunker, 1992) have been administered in drinking water at levels of 0.050 and 0.075%. As a result of both studies, no difference was found from the classical

methods in terms of water and feed intake, live weight and mortality rate. However, it has been reported that the addition of methionine to the drinking water of broilers reduces stress and mortality rates as a result of its practical application (Anonymous, 1984). It has been reported that the addition of methionine to the drinking water of laying hens has no negative effect on the live weight, feed and water consumption and egg production of laying hens (Cadirci, 2001, Cadirci et al., 2009). Poultry can reduce their feed intake under stress conditions (high temperature, rapid temperature changes, density, etc.) while keeping their water consumption at normal levels or even above (North and Bell, 1990), thus ensuring uninterrupted methionine intake. The aim of this study is to compare the performance of animals at different temperatures by administering methionine to them with water, in addition to the classical methods known.

MATERIALS and METHODS

The study was carried out in two rooms, each measuring 5 x 5 m, in the Poultry Research Unit of the Faculty of Agriculture, Harran University, with roof and wall insulation. The research was conducted in November and December when the ambient temperature was below 20 °C. In this study, 288 one day old mixed sex broiler chicks (Ross ® 308) were used. Room temperatures were maintained at commercial standards for the first 21 days, and for the last 21 days, the rooms were kept at 22 and 30 °C with the help of thermostatic heaters. A lighting program of 23 hours light and 1 hour dark was applied during the trial. All chicks were kept together for the first three weeks. From the third week to the end of the sixth week, three groups of 48 animals were formed in all treatment groups for each temperature and the minimum live weight difference between treatments was considered. Then, each group was divided into 24 subgroups, each consisting of two animals. The cages forming the subgroups are 50x50x50 cm in size. Three different rations were used during the research (Table 1). Rations were made in a 30 kg mixer located in the Poultry Research Unit of Harran University Faculty of Agriculture. In order to eliminate possible differences in particle size between rations, corn and soybean meal were crushed uniformly in the special hammer mill in the unit. The starter diet (Diet 1) was formulated taking into account nutrient content (NRC, 1994). All chicks were fed Diet 1 for the first three weeks. At the end of the third week, three groups were formed for each different temperature. The control group (G1) was fed with diet 2 and normal water. Diet 2 the nutrient specifications were set to meet or exceed NRC (1994) nutrient requirements where level of methionine in feed was 3.8 g/kg. Group 2 (G2) was fed with diet 3 and water with 0.050 methionine and group 3 (G3) with diet 3 and water with 0.075 methionine until the end of the trial. In fact, diet 2 is like diet 3 but without the added methionine so that the calculated level of methionine in the feed was 3.1 g/kg. The feed consumption of the experimental animals for the first three weeks was measured collectively. The total feed consumed was divided by the number of chicks and individual feed consumption of the chicks was accepted as equal. Feed consumption in the last three weeks was determined by measuring the feeders of each experimental unit. During the course of the experiment all birds were fed ad libitum and every effort was made to ensure their welfare. Two liter waterers with nipples attached to the bottom were installed in each experimental unit. The height of the water bowl is adjusted to make it easier for animals to drink water in parallel with their growth. Methionine and normal water, in determined volumes considering the treatment groups, were added to the waterers daily. Methionine solutions were mixed weekly in tap water in large (60 L) plastic containers and provided ad libitum via plastic watering bottles with nipples (2000 mL), according to the design of the experiment. At the end of the experiment, the animals were starved overnight and then slaughtered. Wing numbered animals were slaughtered to prevent mixing of treatment groups. Dry plucking was done, internal organs of the animals were removed and the carcass was cut into pieces according to (Şenköylü 1991). All measurements during the trial and feed preparation were made with a BL 6100 Sartorius brand scale with 0.1 gr sensitivity. Feed consumption in the first three weeks was obtained by dividing the total consumption of chicks fed together by the number of animals. Feed consumption in the last three weeks was determined as a result of daily measurements by leaving more feed than each treatment could eat at a specified time of day in each experimental unit. At the end of the experiment, all animals were weighed alive and the carcass elements were measured after slaughtering, taking into account the wing numbers. Feed utilization was calculated by adding the feed consumption of each experimental unit in the last three weeks to the average feed consumption of the first 3 weeks and dividing by the live weight. No animals died during the study period. General Linear Model was applied to all data obtained in Windows-based SPSS statistics program. The LSD

(Least Significant Difference) test was also applied to determine the differences in means where differences between groups were observed (SPSS, 1992).

Table 1. Ingredient and nutrient composition of experimental diets.

Ingredient composition, %	Diet 1	Diet 2	Diet 3
Corn, 7.57% CP	46.02	56.73	56.68
Soybean, 46.36% CP	41.92	33.80	33.89
Maize oil	5.82	6.18	6.20
Limestone	1.34	1.40	1.40
Dicalcium phosphate [©]	1.6	1.15	1.15
NaCl	0.46	0.33	0.33
Vit./Min. Premix [#]	0.25	0.25	0.25
Anticoccidials	0.10	0.10	0.10
DL-Methionine	0.15	0.06	-
Nutrient composition			
Crude protein [¶] , %	23	20	20
Calcium [¶] , %	1	0.9	0.9
Available phosphorus [¶] , %	0.45	0.35	0.35
Sodium [¶] , %	0.20	0.15	0.15
Arginine [¶] , %	1.61	1.37	1.37
Isoleucine [¶] , %	1.08	0.86	0.86
Leucine [¶] , %	1.94	1.75	1.75
Lysine [¶] , %	1.32	1.11	1.11
Methionine [¶] , %	0.50	0.38	0.31
Methionine + cystine [¶] , %	0.88	0.72	0.65
Threonine [¶] , %	0.90	0.78	0.78
Tryptophan [¶] , %	0.28	0.24	0.24
ME, kcal/kg [¶] 3200	3200	3200	3200

ME, metabolisable energy. [©]The composition of dicalcium phosphate provided the following amounts per kg: Ca 230 g and P 200g; [#]composition of vitamins and minerals in the premix provided the following amounts per kg of diet: vitamin A, 15,000 U; vitamin D3, 2500 U; vitamin E, 40 mg; vitamin K3, 5 mg; vitamin B1, 3 mg; vitamin B2, 7 mg; vitamin B6, 5 mg; vitamin B12, 0.02 mg; pan-totenic acid, 10 mg; niacin, 40 mg; folic acid, 1 mg; biotin, 0.07 mg; Mn, 80 mg; Fe, 60 mg; Zn, 60 mg; Cu, 5 mg; I, 1 mg; Co, 0.2 mg; Se, 0.15 mg; cholin chloride, 300 mg; [¶]based on analysis of maize and soybean meal; [¶]based on NRC 1994 values for maize, soybean meal, DL-Methionine and maize oil.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

The results for total feed intake, final body weight and feed conversion ratio of birds consuming methionine given either in feed or water at two environmental temperatures during the 21 days of the experiment are shown in Table 2. Significant interaction was not observed between environmental temperature and methionine administration method. Hereby, primary attention is directed to the main effects of environmental temperature and the method of delivery on total feed intake, final body weight and feed conversion ratio. A significant reduction ($P < 0.05$) of total feed intake, final body weight and feed conversion ratio was observed at 30°C compared to 22°C. Increases in environmental temperature have been shown to have a negative effect on the growth rate of broilers (Howlader and Rose, 1987; Liu et al., 2020). Probably, the main reason for this negative effect of high temperature on performance may be reduced feed intake (Hurwitz et al., 1980; Oluwagbenga and Fraley, 2023). A greater reduction in growth than in feed intake resulting in a depressed feed efficiency. These findings are consistent with (Gerard et al., 1996). Therefore, it appears that under the conditions of this study, the reduced feed intake and lower body weight gain associated with high temperature in broilers cannot be eliminated by the addition of methionine to the drinking water. These findings are largely in agreement with the results of Cadirci and Koncagul, (2014).

Significant differences ($P < 0.05$) were found among the effects of dietary treatments on total feed intake, final body weight and feed conversion ratio (Table 2). This difference was not observed in total feed consumption, final body weight and feed conversion ratio when methionine was added to feed (G1) or water at 0.075% (G3) but was observed only when methionine was added to water at 0.050% (G2). The lower total

feed intake and final body weight in G2 is probably due to the deficiency of methionine amino acid in the diet. If a bird is undersupplied of a first limiting amino acid (e.g. methionine) for a day, the average rate of feed intake and thereby output will decrease (Cadirci et al., 2009). On the other hand, it is likely that the decrease in growth was less than the decrease in feed intake, resulting in a decrease in feed conversion ratio. Similarly, Sohail et al., (2012) found that broilers exposed to chronic heat stress had reduced feed intake and body weight, and higher feed consumption rate.

Table 2. Total feed intake, final body weight and feed conversion ratio of birds consuming methionine in either feed or water at 22 and 30°C.

21-42 days of age	T, °C		G			P		
	22	30	G1	G2	G3	T	D	TxD
TFI (g)	3995.9 ^a	3748.5 ^b	3942.4 ^a	3662.8 ^b	4012.3 ^a	0.009	0.007	0.862
FBW (g)	2354.0 ^a	2248.0 ^b	2330.6 ^a	2205.6 ^b	2366.8 ^a	0.015	0.007	0.834
FCR(g/g)	1.69 ^a	1.66 ^b	1.69 ^a	1.66 ^b	1.69 ^a	0.001	0.007	0.880

T, temperature; G, diets; G1, control diet; G2, without supplemental methionine control diet + 0.050%-added from feed grade dry DL-methionine in drinking water; G3, without supplemental methionine control diet + 0.075%-added from feed grade dry DL-methionine in drinking water; TFI, total feed intake; FBW, final body weight; FCR, feed conversion ratio; mean for temperature (n=36 replicate) and dietary (n=24 replicate) treatments. ^{ab} Means in a row within the same treatment with different superscripts differ significantly (P<0.05).

Table 3 shows weight of eviscerated carcass and carcass parts (drums, thighs, de-boned breast and abdominal fat), of broiler slaughtered at 42 days of age. No significant interaction of temperature and diet was observed, therefore, only the main effects for temperatures and dietary treatments are presented. Austic (1985), Leenstra and Cahaner (1991) and Borges et al. (2004) reported that broilers kept in high ambient temperature produce less whole carcass weight, and this decrease is particularly evident in breast meat (Howliver and Rose, 1989).

Our observations showed similarity with these findings: high environmental temperature significantly reduced final body weight and de-boned breast. In contrast, eviscerated carcass, drums, thighs and wings weight was unaffected by environmental temperature: the negative effect of high temperature was not sufficiently great to result in significant difference between the low and high temperature groups. The results remark that the growth of breast was suppressed more severely compare to eviscerated carcass, drums, thighs and wings. The eviscerated carcass, drums, thighs and wings were suppressed to a lesser extent than de-boned breast. Therefore, in agreement with the findings of Gu et al. (2008), the results of the present study suggest that the growth of de-boned breast is more sensitive to high environmental temperature. In this study, weight of abdominal fat significantly increased with the increase of temperature. These findings are consistent with Baziz et al. (1996) who suggested that a high environmental temperature may facilitate the development of abdominal fat.

Table 3. Eviscerated carcass, major carcass parts yield and abdominal fat of birds consuming methionine in either feed or water at 22 and 30°C.

21-42 days of age	T, °C		G			P		
	22	30	G1	G2	G3	T	D	TxD
Carcass (g)	1530.7	1469.2	1515.2 ^{ab}	1436.7 ^b	1553.3 ^a	0.128	0.050	0.838
Drums (g)	219.2	220.7	222.7	211.2	226.3	0.762	0.107	0.970
Thighs (g)	289.0	279.7	289.7	272.0	292.1	0.316	0.142	0.885
Wings (g)	142.0	135.7	139.9	134.6	142.6	0.065	0.149	0.758
De-boned breast (g)	450.4 ^a	420.2 ^b	444.1 ^a	411.0 ^b	452.8 ^a	0.015	0.014	0.835
Abdominal fat (g)	30.9 ^a	34.6 ^b	33.0	32.9	32.1	0.042	0.936	0.394

T, temperature; G, diets; G1, control diet; G2, without supplemental methionine control diet + 0.050%-added from feed grade dry DL-methionine in drinking water; G3, without supplemental methionine control diet + 0.075%-added from feed grade dry DL-methionine in drinking water; mean for temperature (n=72 replicate) and dietary (n=48 replicate) treatments. ^{ab} Means in a row within the same treatment with different superscripts differ significantly (P<0.05).

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Significant differences ($P < 0.05$) were found among the effects of dietary treatments eviscerated carcass and de-boned breast weight (Table 3). But, this difference was not observed in eviscerated carcass and de-boned breast weight when methionine was added to feed (G1) or water at 0.075% (G3) but was observed only when methionine was added to water at 0.050% (G2). The lower total eviscerated carcass and de-boned breast weight in G2 is probably due to the deficiency of methionine amino acid in the diet. No significant effects of different dietary treatments on drums, thighs, wings and abdominal fat were observed. In agreement with previous reports (Damron and Goodson Williams, 1987; Damron and Flunker, 1992), our study showed that 0.075% methionine administered into the drinking water of broiler chickens had no adverse effects on the performance and carcass yield of the birds.

CONCLUSION

Adding methionine to the birds' drinking water makes it easy to adjust the methionine level according to need without the need to re-mix the feed, thus saving the producer the cost of extra equipment, time and labor required during feed preparation. The benefit of this method is that the birds are constantly provided with methionine. More dosage levels are needed to confirm the effectiveness of administering methionine in water compared to feed.

Conflicts of Interest: The author(s) declare(s) that there is no conflict of interest regarding this work.

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